

ANALYSIS OF THE LITERARY AND PHILOSOPHICAL IDEAS IN THE PROSE PREFACE OF QUTADGHU BILIG

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16989511>

Abstract. *This article analyzes the content and significance of the prose preface in Yusuf Khass Hajib's "Qutadghu Bilig." It explores the author's ideas on knowledge, justice, reason, ethics, religion, and governance within the socio-cultural context of the 11th century. The study examines the structural and compositional features of the preface, as well as its philosophical and religious motifs, authorial stance, and the linguistic-stylistic devices used in the text. The article highlights how the preface lays the conceptual foundations for the entire work, particularly regarding the role of knowledge and justice in societal development. It contributes to a deeper understanding of "Qutadghu Bilig" as a philosophical-literary heritage.*

Keywords: *prose preface, Qutadghu Bilig, Yusuf Khass Hajib, knowledge, justice, intellect, religion, language and style, author's stance, philosophical motif, literary heritage.*

Introduction

The work "Qutadghu Bilig" ("Knowledge that Leads to Happiness"), which occupies a significant place in the history of Turkish literature, belongs to the pen of Yusuf Khass Hajib, who lived and worked in the 11th century, and is an important source for its time, filled with not only literary and artistic, but also philosophical, political and social content. The prose introduction of the work serves not only as a key to the author's intention, but also as a unique expression of the socio-political, spiritual and philosophical worldviews that prevailed at that time.

Main Part

The prose introduction of the work is unique in form and content, embodying the main ideas and intentions of the author. In this section, Yusuf Khass Hajib not only assesses his time, but also clearly expresses the reasons for writing the work and the socio-spiritual goals it pursues. Although the structure of the prologue is based on Islamic religious traditions, its content is enriched with deep secular, moral and political reflections.

1. Structural and compositional structure of the prose prologue.

The prose prologue of the work "Qutadghu Bilig" contains a compositional structure typical of traditional Islamic literature. The author Yusuf Khass Hajib begins this section with praise of Allah. He acknowledges that the Creator created the world from nothing and endowed man with reason and language, and expresses gratitude: "Uttering this word, first of all, let us thank the Creator, the Almighty, the Great, who created the world from nothing, created man, endowed him with reason, created language and taught him to speak." With these sentences, the author emphasizes that thought and speech are the highest blessings bestowed upon humanity.

The author then blesses the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings be upon him) and praises his blessedness as a mercy to humanity: "Muhammad Mustafa is the Messenger of Allah, he was sent as a mercy to all creation, he brought the truth, he destroyed ignorance." In this way, the author demonstrates his deep faith in Islamic values and the prophet.

In the next paragraph, Yusuf Khass Hajib openly expresses his attitude towards science. He highly values the possessors of knowledge – scientists – and highly values their place in society: “Whoever does not seek knowledge will remain in darkness; whoever listens to the words of scientists and acts on them will be saved.” With these arguments, the author implies that he considers ignorance to be darkness, and knowledge to be the source of salvation.

At the end of the introduction, the author clearly formulates his main purpose for writing the work. He emphasizes that he wrote this book for kings who must learn to rule justly and lead the people to a peaceful life: “I have written this book for kings so that they read it and rule the state justly, and the people live in peace.” This sentence shows that the work is permeated with not only theoretical but also practical values.

2. Harmony of philosophical and religious motives

Yusuf Khass Hajib relies on Islamic beliefs when writing his work. According to him, science is a means that leads man to perfection. In the introduction, praising Allah, it is obvious that the author’s thoughts are in harmony with the religious basis. He also expresses his devotion to the Islamic tradition by sending blessings upon Muhammad (peace be upon him). Through these aspects, the preface expresses a balance between religion and secularism, personal faith and social responsibility.

“Blessed is he who has knowledge, and he who remains ignorant is humiliated. Reason is man's guide, and religion is his lamp. He who does not follow these two paths will perish in heedlessness.”

This passage shows that in the author's thinking, science and religion are viewed as complementary forces. For Yusuf Khass Hajib, reason is the comprehension of worldly truth, and religion is the source of spiritual light. He interprets science as a means of saving man from ignorance, and religious faith as a means of saving man from a spiritual crisis. Thus, the author puts forward a balanced position between religion and secular thinking: not only a believer, but also a knowledgeable person should be the main support of society.

This approach also reflects the synthesis of Islamic philosophy and the Turkish worldview of that time: along with the call for perfection on a religious basis, the fulfillment of social duties in this world is promoted, that is, fair governance, moral maturity.

3. The concept of knowledge and justice.

One of the most frequently encountered concepts in the introduction is "knowledge", which Yusuf Khass Hajib defines as the force that saves man from ignorance. In his opinion, a true ruler is a knowledgeable, wise and just person. In the prose introduction to the work, these ideas are first presented as a theoretical basis and are consistently developed throughout the work.

“Rule the state wisely, rule the people with knowledge. An ignorant ruler allows oppression, and an unreasonable judge incurs wrath.”

This passage clearly expresses the author’s point of view on the inseparable connection between knowledge and justice. He considers ignorance to be the root of oppression, and stupidity to be the cause of destruction. According to the author, in order for justice to prevail in governing the state, the ruler must be knowledgeable and wise.

Based on these considerations, it can be said that the prose introduction defines the main theoretical criteria for the concepts of knowledge and justice in “Qutadghu Bilig” and interprets them as the basis for social development.

4. Period and the author's position

In the prose preface, Yusuf Khass Hajib openly outlines his life and creative path, as well as his critical attitude towards his time. He connects the need to write the work with the decline of moral and human values of his time. It is here that the author describes himself as an intellectual who "transforms himself through the word," that is, confronts the moral and spiritual crisis.

"Times have changed, people have lost their way, turned away from the truth; and I wanted to show this way, I wanted to awaken hearts with the right word."

This passage clearly demonstrates Yusuf Khass Hajib's sense of social responsibility, his civic position as a writer and his awareness of the pain of the time. He emphasizes that he created the work with the intention of reforming society and showing the right path with the power of words.

"I wrote this word so that it would benefit the people, show the way to the leader and warn the ignorant."

In this sentence, the author presents his work as a socio-spiritual guide. He wants this work to be useful not only to the rulers, but also to the people and various layers of society. He sees every word of the work as a force that awakens people.

"I have traveled a lot, seen a lot, and I am not satisfied; I wrote these words so that they become a monument to me and the people."

Here Yusuf Khass Hajib appears not only as a teacher, but also as an intellectual who felt the pain of his time, expressed his opinions and left behind a legacy. He sees his work as a source that will stand the test of time and be of eternal use to people.

In general, in the introduction, Yusuf Khass Hajib describes himself as a witness of historical changes, a writer seeking answers to social problems, and a spiritual leader seeking to atone for sins with words. This position makes "Qutadghu Bilig" important not only as a literary document, but also as a cultural, philosophical, and political document.

5. Language and stylistic features.

Yusuf Khass Hajib's prose introduction is distinguished by its simplicity, coherence, and linguistic closeness to the people. The work skillfully combines Arabic and Persian religious and philosophical terms with folk expressions in the native Turkic language. It is thanks to this approach that the text has not only scientific and philosophical depth, but also gives aesthetic and spiritual pleasure.

"Before pronouncing this word, it is necessary to thank God, who gave man language, gave him reason, and taught him to make words beautiful. "

This passage is simple in structure, understandable and close to the vernacular. It provides a natural flow of thought thanks to a structure not alien to the modern reader - such phrases as "he gave language, he gave reason". Here one can clearly feel the author's mastery in conveying high spiritual ideas in a vernacular form.

"Praise be to Allah, Muhammad Mustafa is the light of the message, mercy for the people."

In this sentence, religious and Arabic-Persian concepts such as "Allah", "praise", "message", "ummah", "respect" are introduced into the colloquial language in a way not alien to the colloquial language. They deepen the content of the text, enhance the religious-aesthetic effect and reflect Islamic thinking.

"Time has passed, the path is lost, people are confused; these words are the gates to the truth."

Here, complex spiritual concepts such as "lost" and "truth" are enclosed in a simple and understandable grammatical structure. Thus, Yusuf Khass Hajib illuminated complex

philosophical ideas in a language close to colloquial, which makes it relevant both for his time and today.

“Language is the soul of man, reason is his guide, the heart is his state, but if these three are not united, man will suffer.”

This sentence is an example of the use of artistic-figurative and symbolic means of expressing language. The author turns abstract concepts (language, reason, heart) into living images through allegory. This technique gives the text not only depth, but also literary and aesthetic beauty.

Speaking about science, religion and morality in a prose introduction, Yusuf Khass Hajib skillfully illuminates complex ideas with the simplicity of the Turkish language. Arabic-Persian terms translate the text into a scientific and philosophical context. This style allows the work to be presented in an impressive and modern form not only for its time, but also for the modern reader.

6. Relevance for the Present Time

The ideas put forward in the prose introduction by Yusuf Khass Hajib are still relevant today. Speaking about science, justice, fairness, public administration and moral maturity, he presents us with ideas that are still relevant in the 21st century. In particular, the approach to science, the criteria of justice and the issues of personal responsibility in the education of a mature personality are still relevant today.

Functional analysis of ideological concepts in the prose introduction. Table 1.1.

Idea/concept	The function of prose in prose	Role in society	Relevance for today
Science/knowledge	The light that saves man from ignorance, the source of wisdom	Raising a smart person	Foundations of critical thinking and digital literacy
Intelligence/Thinking	The main tool in conducting state affairs	Criteria for determining leadership potential	Innovative decisions, information analysis
Justice	Central principle in public administration	Organizational stability and social trust	Legal awareness, transparency and accountability
Religion/belief	Moral criterion, source of spiritual stability	Humanism, education of conscience	Spiritual health, social cohesion
Morality/Virtue	The main criterion that calls for unity of word and deed	Personal responsibility, social discipline	Formation of professional ethics
The power of words/thoughts	A tool for reform, the author's main weapon	The power to change public consciousness	Raising social awareness through literature and the press

Conclusion

The prose preface to the work "Qutadghu Bilig" is a unique source that illuminates the social and philosophical life of its time, the ancient idea of government based on the harmony of justice and knowledge. In this section, Yusuf Khass Hajib teaches us a great lesson: a happy society can be achieved through a combination of science and justice. Therefore, the prose preface should be perceived not only as a "door" to the work, but also as a gateway to an entire philosophical concept.

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